

State Observation and Parameter Estimation in Cyclic Pursuit Systems

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Abstract—This paper addresses estimation of states and control parameters in cyclic pursuit systems. Classical observability tests are employed to derive conditions under which system states (i.e. agent positions) are observable in several types of cyclic pursuit schemes, including constant bearing and beacon-referenced pursuit systems. Under straightforward conditions on the system control parameters, it is demonstrated that the relative positions and control parameters of the other agents (as well as the beacon, when applicable) can be accurately estimated by an observer agent based only on direct sensing of one neighbor. Since the observer node can be viewed as an infiltrator agent, the results suggest applications in characterizing unknown members of a collective.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collectives of interacting autonomous agents (also referred to as “multi-agent systems” or “relative sensing networks”) have received considerable research attention over the last two decades. Such systems have been analyzed in terms of stability, communication topology, and varying control methods, and in the current work we consider the observability of states and estimation of parameters in multi-agent systems. We are motivated by a scenario in which an infiltrator agent, capable only of directly sensing one other agent in the collective, endeavors to determine the states and control parameters of the other agents in the collective.

State observability in multi-agent systems has been explored in works such as [1], where the authors analyzed “relative sensing networks” for conditions under which components of the node dynamics would be observable. Zelazo and Mesbahi provided additional results in [2], [3], demonstrating that initial states were unobservable for systems in which each agent had the same dynamics, but heterogeneous dynamics often results in observability. In [4], the authors consider observability in systems with an undirected cycle graph (i.e., agent i is influenced by agent $i - 1$ and agent $i + 1$). We also note [5], which addresses the estimation of velocity and its derivatives for the agents in a collective based on knowledge of a finite sample of observed positions.

In the current work, we analyze observability of states and estimation of parameters in the particular context of cyclic pursuit systems (i.e. agent i pursues agent $i + 1$, modulo the number of agents [6]) and cyclic pursuit systems with beacon reference [7], [8], based only on direct sensing of the relative configuration between two of the agents. Our approach is

based on applying classical tests for state observability to linear versions of the cyclic pursuit system. Of note, we demonstrate that though the absolute positions of the agents with respect to a fixed inertial frame are not observable based on the limited sensing paradigm, the relative positions of the other agents (and of the beacon, when applicable) are observable under some straightforward conditions on the control parameters. (See *Proposition 2.2* and *Proposition 2.4.*) We note that the work in [9] considers similar problems, but restricts its focus to a special case of cyclic pursuit systems based on classical pursuit, common pursuit gain, and sensing of absolute state.

The paper is divided into three main sections. In Section II, we analyze state observability for four types of cyclic pursuit systems: 1) classical pursuit, 2) constant bearing (CB) pursuit, 3) beacon-referenced classical pursuit, and 4) beacon-referenced CB pursuit. For the first two systems, we derive conditions for observability of the relative states of the agents. For the beacon-referenced systems, we address observability for several low-dimensional cases by direct calculation, leading to a conjecture regarding the observability characteristics for systems of arbitrary size (to be proved in future work). In Section III, we address parameter observability in cyclic pursuit systems through augmentation of the state vector, focusing on the 3-agent case to derive conditions for observability of the augmented state. Finally, Section IV presents simulations illustrating the theoretical results of the previous sections.

II. OBSERVABILITY OF STATES IN CYCLIC PURSUIT SYSTEMS

The kinematics of a system of n planar agents $\mathbf{r}_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ can be modeled most simply with a single integrator, i.e. the motion of each of the n agents is described by

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}}_i = \mathbf{u}_i, \quad (1)$$

for some control input $\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$. If the position coordinates are decoupled for a particular control \mathbf{u}_i , we can simplify the notation by treating the coordinates independently, i.e. consider $r_i \in \mathbb{R}$ without loss of generality.

The motion of the agents in such a collective is determined by the interaction graph as well as by the feedback laws implemented by the individual agents. In what follows, we will consider both the cycle graph, where agent i responds to agent $i + 1$, modulo n , as well as the “cycle with beacon” graph, in which agent i responds to agent $i + 1$ as well as some fixed beacon. The feedback laws we use are based on variations of a classical pursuit law as well as a constant bearing pursuit law. In each case, we consider the

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observability of states from the perspective of a single agent (always considered to be agent 1 in this paper), with the constraint that the observer agent may only directly sense the relative state between itself and the next agent, $\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2$.

A. Observability of states under cyclic classical pursuit

We start by considering the case in which each agent employs the classical pursuit law

$$\mathbf{u}_i = k_i(\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (2)$$

where $k_i > 0$ is a control gain parameter, and addition in the indices is interpreted modulo n . Since the kinematics for the position coordinates are decoupled (and redundant) under this control law, we simplify our analysis by defining the n -agent state vector $\mathbf{r} = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n)$, so that our kinematic equations of motion in matrix form are

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = \begin{bmatrix} -k_1 & k_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -k_2 & k_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -k_{n-1} & k_{n-1} \\ k_n & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -k_n \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}. \quad (3)$$

Define the $(n \times n)$ system matrix as A , noting that it is always rank-deficient and can be factored as

$$A = K_{n \times (n-1)} P_{(n-1) \times n} \quad (4)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} -k_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -k_2 & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -k_{n-1} \\ k_n & k_n & k_n & k_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

We are interested in the observability of system states based on agent 1's sensing of $r_1 - r_2$, and our first result demonstrates that the system (3) is not observable under this constrained sensing paradigm.

Proposition 2.1: The system (3) with measurements $y = r_1 - r_2$ is not observable.

Proof: Letting \hat{P} be the $n \times n$ matrix given by P with an added last row of 0's with a 1 in the last entry, we have the similarity transformation

$$\mathbf{z} = \hat{P}\mathbf{r} = [r_1 - r_2, r_2 - r_3, \dots, r_{n-1} - r_n, r_n]^T, \quad (5)$$

with associated kinematics

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \hat{A}\mathbf{z} = \hat{P}A\hat{P}^{-1}\mathbf{z}. \quad (6)$$

Note that \hat{P}^{-1} is an upper-triangular matrix with all 1's on the diagonal and above and all 0's below the diagonal; therefore the last column of $A\hat{P}^{-1}$ is all zeros. This means that the last column of $\hat{A} = \hat{P}A\hat{P}^{-1}$ is all zeros, which implies that the last column of \hat{A}^ℓ is all zeros for any $\ell = 1, 2, \dots$. Thus, for $y = r_1 - r_2 = C\mathbf{z}$ with $C = [1, 0, 0, \dots, 0]$, the last column of the observability matrix

$$\mathcal{O} = [C; C\hat{A}; C\hat{A}^2; \dots; C\hat{A}^{n-1}]_{n \times n} \quad (7)$$

is all zeros and therefore not full rank. (Here we have used the semi-colon to denote a new row in the matrix.) ■

Though *Proposition 2.1* establishes that absolute system states are not observable based on a single observation of relative state, the relative states are observable under the same sensing paradigm. Defining the $(n-1)$ -length vector of relative system states by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}} \triangleq P\mathbf{r} = [r_1 - r_2, r_2 - r_3, \dots, r_{n-1} - r_n]^T, \quad (8)$$

one can make use of the matrix decomposition from (4) to derive associated (reduced) kinematics for $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ as

$$\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}} = P\dot{\mathbf{r}} = P(A\mathbf{r}) = PKP\mathbf{r} = PK\tilde{\mathbf{r}}. \quad (9)$$

The $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ system matrix $\tilde{A} \triangleq PK$ is

$$\tilde{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -k_1 & k_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -k_2 & k_3 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -k_{n-2} & k_{n-1} \\ -k_n & -k_n & \dots & -k_n & -(k_{n-1} + k_n) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

Proposition 2.2: The system of relative states given by (9) is observable based on measurements $y = r_1 - r_2 = [1, 0, 0, \dots, 0] \tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ if and only if $k_i > 0$ for $i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1$.

Proof: Note that the matrix \tilde{A} has all zeros above the first superdiagonal, and therefore the matrix \tilde{A}^ℓ has all zeros above the ℓ -th superdiagonal. Thus, for $C = [1, 0, 0, \dots, 0]$, the observability matrix

$$\tilde{\mathcal{O}} = [C; C\tilde{A}; C\tilde{A}^2; \dots; C\tilde{A}^{n-2}]_{(n-1) \times (n-1)} \quad (11)$$

is lower-triangular, and therefore its determinant is given by the product of the diagonal entries. We proceed by demonstrating that the diagonal entries are given by

$$\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{ii} = \prod_{j=2}^i k_j, \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1, \quad (12)$$

as follows. Since $C\tilde{A} = [-k_1 \ k_2 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]$, it is clear that (12) is satisfied for $i = 2$. Now suppose (12) is satisfied for some $i < n-1$. Then denoting $\tilde{A} = [\tilde{a}_{ij}]$, by direct calculation we have

$$\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{i+1, i+1} = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{ij} \tilde{a}_{j, i+1} = \sum_{j=1}^i \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{ij} \tilde{a}_{j, i+1} = \tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{ii} \tilde{a}_{i, i+1} = \prod_{j=2}^{i+1} k_j,$$

where we have used the structure of \tilde{A} and the fact that $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}$ is lower-triangular. By induction, (12) holds for all $i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1$, and therefore the determinant of the observability matrix $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}$ is given by $\det(\tilde{\mathcal{O}}) = k_2^{n-2} k_3^{n-3} \dots k_{n-2}^2 k_{n-1}$. Thus, $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}$ has full rank (i.e. the system (\tilde{A}, C) is observable) if and only if $k_i > 0$ for $i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1$. ■

Remark: *Proposition 2.2* demonstrates that if the gains of agents 2 through $n-1$ are all positive, then the observability matrix is full-rank, i.e. the relative states of all the agents in the collective can be estimated by agent 1 based only on direct sensing of the relative state of agent 2. However, Monte Carlo simulation of 1000 trials of randomly selected parameter values and varying numbers of agents reveals that the minimum eigenvalue of the observability Gramian

Fig. 1. The average minimum eigenvalue of the observability Gramian plotted as a function of the number of agents, based on simulation of 1000 trials of randomly selected parameter values.

approaches zero when the number of agents in the collective is greater than 6, as depicted in Figure 1. One approach to mitigating this effect would be to increase the number of observer agents, an avenue to be explored in future research.

B. Observability of states under cyclic CB pursuit

This section considers the two-dimensional system (1) with the CB (or “rotated”) pursuit law [10] given by

$$\mathbf{u}_i = k_i R(\alpha_i)(\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (13)$$

where $k_i > 0$ is a gain parameter, $\alpha_i \in (-\pi, \pi]$ is a pursuit angle parameter, and $R(\alpha_i) \in SO(2)$ is the rotation matrix

$$R(\alpha_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha_i) & -\sin(\alpha_i) \\ \sin(\alpha_i) & \cos(\alpha_i) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

In this case the position coordinate kinematics are coupled so that the full state vector is $\mathbf{r} = (\mathbf{r}_1^T, \mathbf{r}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{r}_n^T)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ and the closed-loop kinematics are

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = A_\alpha \mathbf{r}, \quad (15)$$

where the $(2n \times 2n)$ matrix A_α takes the same form as (3) with $k_i R(\alpha_i)$ taking the place of the scalar k_i entries.

Proposition 2.3: The system (15) with measurements $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2$ is not observable.

Proof: The proof follows the proof of *Proposition 2.1* with block matrix operations. ■

As in Section II-A, the reduced dimension version of (15) with relative states $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i = \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_{i+1}$ has kinematics

$$\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}} = \tilde{A}_\alpha \tilde{\mathbf{r}}, \quad (16)$$

where the $(2n-2) \times (2n-2)$ matrix \tilde{A}_α has the same form as (10) with $k_i R(\alpha_i)$ taking the place of the scalar k_i entries. This suggests the following, analogous to *Proposition 2.2*.

Proposition 2.4: The system of relative states given by (16) is observable based on measurements $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2 = [\mathbb{1}, 0, \dots, 0] \tilde{\mathbf{r}}$, where $\mathbb{1}$ is the 2×2 identity matrix, if and only if $k_i > 0$ for $i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1$.

Proof: Steps analogous to the proof of *Proposition 2.2* can be used to demonstrate that the $(2n-2) \times (2n-2)$

observability matrix $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}$ is block lower-triangular with blocks on the diagonal (for $i = 2, 3, \dots, n-1$) given by

$$\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{ii} = \prod_{j=2}^i k_j R(\alpha_j) = \left(\prod_{j=2}^i k_j \right) R \left(\sum_{\ell=2}^i \alpha_\ell \right). \quad (17)$$

Thus $\det(\tilde{\mathcal{O}}_{ii}) = \left(\prod_{j=2}^i k_j \right)^2$ (based on the properties of rotation matrices), and since the determinant of a block lower-triangular matrix is given by the product of the determinants of the blocks on the diagonal, we have

$$\det(\tilde{\mathcal{O}}) = (k_2^{n-2} k_3^{n-3} \dots k_{n-2}^2 k_{n-1})^2, \quad (18)$$

which establishes the claims. ■

C. Observability of states under beacon-referenced cyclic classical pursuit

Recent work [8], [11], [12] analyzed beacon-referenced (or “target-centric”) cyclic pursuit systems in which each agent i responds to both agent $i+1$ as well as to a fixed beacon. Letting $\mathbf{r}_b \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote the location of the beacon, we introduce a beacon-referenced version of the classical pursuit law (2) which takes the form

$$\mathbf{u}_i = (1 - \lambda_i) k_i (\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i) + \lambda_i k_i (\mathbf{r}_b - \mathbf{r}_i), \quad (19)$$

where $\lambda_i \in [0, 1]$ determines the relative influence of the beacon. Since the position coordinates are decoupled under control (19), we again simplify the analysis by considering one coordinate. Define the state vector $\mathbf{r}_e = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n, r_b)$ with r_i serving as a shorthand for $r_{i,1}$. Also denote

$$f_i \triangleq (1 - \lambda_i) k_i \quad g_i \triangleq \lambda_i k_i, \quad (20)$$

so that the closed-loop kinematics take the form

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}}_e = A_e \mathbf{r}_e, \quad (21)$$

where A_e is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} -f_1 - g_1 & f_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & g_1 \\ 0 & -f_2 - g_2 & f_2 & 0 & \dots & 0 & g_2 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ f_n & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -f_n - g_n & g_n \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

Note the $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ matrix A_e can be factored as

$$A_e = K_b P_b, \quad (22)$$

where the $(n+1) \times n$ matrix K_b is obtained by removing the last column of A_e , and the $n \times (n+1)$ matrix P_b is the $n \times n$ identity matrix with an added column of -1 entries on the righthand side.

Similar to *Proposition 2.1*, the following proposition proves that the beacon referenced system is not observable with measurement of a single relative position.

Proposition 2.5: The system (21) with measurements $y = \mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2$ is not observable.

Proof: Let \hat{P}_b be the $(n+1) \times (n+1)$ matrix given by P_b with an added last row of 0's with a 1 in the last entry, such that the similarity transformation

$$\mathbf{z}_e = \hat{P}_b \mathbf{r}_e = [r_1 - r_b, r_2 - r_b, \dots, r_n - r_b, r_b]^T, \quad (23)$$

has associated kinematics

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}}_e = \hat{A}_e \mathbf{z}_e = \hat{P}_b A_e \hat{P}_b^{-1} \mathbf{z}_e. \quad (24)$$

The only nonzero elements of \hat{P}^{-1} are 1's on the diagonal and in the last column, and therefore it follows that the last column of $A_e \hat{P}_b^{-1}$ is all zeros. Following the same steps employed in the proof of *Proposition 2.1*, it holds that the last column of \hat{A}_e^ℓ is all zeros for any $\ell = 1, 2, \dots$. The measurement $y = r_1 - r_2$ is given by $y = C \mathbf{z}_e$ with $C = [1, -1, 0, \dots, 0]$, and it follows that the observability matrix will be rank-deficient since the last column is all zeros. ■

Next, consider a system of relative states, defining the n -dimensional vector of relative system states by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_e \triangleq P_b \mathbf{r}_e = [r_1 - r_b, r_2 - r_b, \dots, r_n - r_b]^T. \quad (25)$$

Making use of (21) and (22), the kinematics of $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_e$ are

$$\dot{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}}_e = P_b \dot{\mathbf{r}}_e = P_b (A_e \mathbf{r}_e) = P_b K_b P_b \mathbf{r}_e = P_b K_b \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_e, \quad (26)$$

giving the $n \times n$ system matrix $\tilde{A}_e \triangleq P_b K_b$ where \tilde{A}_e is the $n \times n$ matrix in the upper left of A_e .

We are interested in the case where agent 1 can only sense the relative state of agent 2 and not the beacon. Therefore, we set $\lambda_1 = 0$ (which results in $g_1 = 0$), removing the beacon-referenced term from agent 1's control (19). We proceed by considering the observability of the system (\tilde{A}_e, C) , with $C = [1, -1, 0, \dots, 0]$ for particular values of n .

1) $n = 2$ case: For $n = 2$ with $g_1 = 0$, straightforward calculations demonstrate that $\det(\tilde{O}_e) = g_2$, and therefore the system is observable if and only if $\lambda_2 k_2 \neq 0$.

2) $n = 3$ case: For $n = 3$, similar calculations lead to

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\tilde{O}_e) &= f_2[(f_2 + g_2)(f_3 + g_3) - f_2 f_3] \\ &= (1 - \lambda_2) k_2^2 k_3 (\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 - \lambda_2 \lambda_3), \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

and thus the system is observable if and only if $k_2 \neq 0$, $k_3 \neq 0$, $\lambda_2 \neq 1$, and $\lambda_2 + \lambda_3 \neq \lambda_2 \lambda_3$.

3) $n = 4$ case: For $n = 4$, similar calculations lead to

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\tilde{O}_e) &= f_2^2 f_3 [(f_2 + g_2)(f_3 + g_3)(f_4 + g_4) - f_2 f_3 f_4] \\ &= (1 - \lambda_2)^2 (1 - \lambda_3) k_2^3 k_3^2 k_4 [1 - (1 - \lambda_2)(1 - \lambda_3)(1 - \lambda_4)]. \end{aligned}$$

This leads one to speculate that the general form for the determinant of the observability matrix is

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\tilde{O}_e) &= \left(\prod_{i=2}^{n-1} f_i^{n-i} \right) \left[\left(\prod_{i=2}^n (f_i + g_i) \right) - \prod_{i=2}^n f_i \right] \\ &= \left(\prod_{i=2}^n k_i^{(n+1-i)} (1 - \lambda_i)^{n-i} \right) \left[1 - \prod_{i=2}^n (1 - \lambda_i) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

This conjecture has been verified by direct calculation up to $n = 9$, and a theoretical proof is the subject of future work.

D. Observability of states under beacon-referenced cyclic CB pursuit

In this last case, we introduce a beacon-referenced version of the CB pursuit law (13) which takes the form

$$u_i = (1 - \lambda_i) k_i R(\alpha_i) (\mathbf{r}_{i+1} - \mathbf{r}_i) + \lambda_i k_i R(\alpha_{ib}) (\mathbf{r}_b - \mathbf{r}_i),$$

where α_i and α_{ib} are pursuit angles with regards to the next agent and the beacon, respectively. Following steps analogous to the previous section, we can define a vector of length $2n$ corresponding to the relative states of the agents with respect to the beacon (i.e. (25) with $\mathbf{r}_i^T - \mathbf{r}_b^T$ for the individual entries). The corresponding $2n \times 2n$ system matrix takes the same form as \tilde{A}_e in the previous section, with $F_i = (1 - \lambda_i) k_i R(\alpha_i)$ replacing the scalar f_i terms and $G_i = \lambda_i k_i R(\alpha_{ib})$ replacing the scalar g_i terms.

$n=3$ case: As before, we set $\lambda_1 = 0$ (i.e. $G_1 = 0$), and we proceed by considering the special case $n = 3$. Making use of the fact that $SO(2)$ is an abelian group (i.e. rotation matrices commute), and letting $C = (\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, 0)$, we obtain our observability matrix

$$\tilde{O}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{1} & -\mathbf{1} & 0 \\ -F_1 & F_1 + F_2 + G_2 & -F_2 \\ F_1^2 - F_2 F_3 & -F_1^2 - (F_2 + G_2)(F_1 + F_2 + G_2) & H \end{bmatrix}$$

where $H = F_2(F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + G_2 + G_3)$. Partitioning \tilde{O}_e as a 2×2 block matrix with $\tilde{O}_{11} = \mathbf{1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \det(\tilde{O}_e) &= \det(\tilde{O}_{11}) \det(\tilde{O}_{22} - \tilde{O}_{21} \tilde{O}_{11}^{-1} \tilde{O}_{12}) \\ &= \det(F_2) \det\left((F_2 + G_2)(F_3 + G_3) - F_2 F_3\right). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Based on (29), one can show that a necessary condition for the system to be observable is $k_2 \neq 0$, $k_3 \neq 0$, and $\lambda_2 \neq 1$.

The similarity between the first line of (27) and the last line of (29) is suggestive that the determinant of the observability matrix this system may have a form analogous to (28), a conjecture that is the subject of future work.

III. OBSERVABILITY OF STATES AND PARAMETERS IN CYCLIC PURSUIT

The observability results of Section II assume agent i has knowledge of every agent's pursuit gain k_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$. This section relaxes the assumption of known agent gains to assess the observability of relative states and gains of all agents. By augmenting the state vector with the unknown gains, the pursuit kinematics of the previous section are nonlinear, such that linear system observability analysis is no longer valid. For a detailed discussion of nonlinear observability the interested reader is referred to [13]. This section derives the observability conditions for $n = 3$ agents in classical pursuit, which is suggestive of observability conditions for the general n -agent cyclic pursuit system.

Consider cyclic pursuit in the reduced kinematics (9). Without loss of generality, assume the perspective of agent $i = 1$. Augmenting the relative position states $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i$ with the time-invariant pursuit gains of other agents in the system gives the state vector $\mathbf{X} = [\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_1, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_2, k_2, k_3]^T = [\tilde{\mathbf{r}}, \mathbf{k}]^T$

$\in \mathbb{R}^{2(n-1)}$. Measurements from the first agent give the nonlinear model

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{X}} &= \begin{bmatrix} -k_1 X_1 + X_3 X_2 \\ -(X_3 + X_4) X_2 - X_4 X_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ y &= [1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0] \mathbf{X}. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Combining the successive Lie derivatives of (30) into the Observability map G and calculating the determinant of $dG = \partial G / \partial \mathbf{x}$ gives

$$\det(dG) = X_3^2 (X_3 - X_4) (-k_1 X_1 X_2 + (X_1 + X_2)(X_2 X_3 + X_1 X_4)). \quad (31)$$

The three agent cyclic pursuit system is locally observable in reduced states and parameters if the observability matrix is full rank [13]. Equivalently, the system is observable if the determinant of the observability rank matrix is non-zero [14]. Equation (31) implies the following.

Proposition 3.1: The three-agent state and parameter cyclic pursuit system is not observable if

- 1) $X_3 = k_2 = 0$
- 2) $X_3 = X_4$, i.e., $k_2 = k_3$
- 3) $-k_1 X_1 X_2 + (X_1 + X_2)(X_2 X_3 + X_1 X_4) = 0$

Proof: Solving for the conditions upon which (31) is zero completes the proof. ■

Condition 1) follows the results of Section II in that the $(i + 1)$ st agent must have positive pursuit gain for agent i to observe the system states and parameters. Since the first agent observes only relative motion between itself and agent two, agent two must be coupled to the remainder of the agents. Condition 2) indicates that agents must have heterogeneous pursuit gains to distinguish between agents. This condition is an artifact of the problem formulation in that each agent's pursuit gain is an augmented state. If gains were assumed equal, the augmented state vector could be reformulated to reduce its dimension. Combining conditions 1) and 2) with the stability criteria of the system implies $k_2 \neq k_3$ and $k_1, k_2, k_3 > 0$ is required to maintain observability, similar to *Proposition 2.2*.

Condition 3) reveals the subspace of state and parameter values resulting in loss of state and parameter observability, which can be divided into two cases. Case 1, where $X_1 = 0$, implies that the state and parameters are not observable if $X_2 = 0$. Therefore, the equilibrium condition at the origin is not observable. Case 2, where $X_1 \neq 0$ and $X_2 \neq 0$, defines a subspace of state configurations at which the system is not observable. Let $\mu = X_1 / X_2$. Solving condition 3) for μ as a function of the parameters k_1 , X_3 , and X_4 gives

$$\mu = \frac{-(X_3 + X_4 - k_1) \pm \sqrt{(X_3 + X_4 - k_1)^2 - 4X_3 X_4}}{2X_3}. \quad (32)$$

Real solutions of (32) define the unobservable state configurations for a given set of parameter values. Numerical analysis reveals the unobservable subspace is primarily limited to gain values $X_3, X_4 < 0.5$ and nonzero μ . Therefore,

perturbations of the system around the origin are observable for a large set of agent pursuit gains. Studies of cyclic pursuit with $n > 3$ agents (omitted for brevity) suggest similar observability conditions in that the agents preceding the agent of interest must have non-zero pursuit gains but the agent following the agent of interest may have zero gain, and all agents must have unique gains in order to distinguish between agents. In addition, state configurations of gain and position combinations can result in loss of observability.

IV. SIMULATIONS AND EXAMPLES

This section provides numerical simulation of the theoretical results in Sections II-D and III. Section IV-A estimates the position of the beacon in the beacon-referenced system of Section II-D, whereas Section IV-B illustrates system identification estimating states and parameters of $n = 3$ agent classical pursuit using measurements collected by one agent.

A. Estimation of Beacon-Relative Positions in CB Beacon Pursuit

This section leverages results of Section II-D, to implement a state observer using measurements from agent 1. Assume agent 1 knows all other agents' parametric pursuit constants $\mathbf{k} = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n]^T$ but measures only the relative position between itself and agent 2. Agent 1's full state estimate be $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$. Agent 1's state observer is designed in the standard observer form [14]

$$\dot{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} = A_e \hat{\mathbf{r}} + L(\mathbf{y} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}), \quad (33)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = C\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, A_e has block matrix form with blocks specified in Section II-D, and the observer gain L is chosen such that $A_e - LC$ is Hurwitz [14].

Figure 2 illustrates simulation of the observer (33) with $n = 3$ agents whose initial position coordinates are distributed randomly in the interval $[-50, 50]$. The left figure illustrates agent trajectories, the actual beacon position (blue square), and the beacon position estimate (dashed black line). The right figure illustrates the actual beacon relative positions of each agent (solid lines) and agent 1's estimated beacon relative positions for each agent (dashed lines). The observer gain L was calculated using pole placement such that the closed loop observer poles are uniformly distributed between -2 and -10 . Note the estimates converge to the actual states.

B. Parameter Estimation via System Identification

The results of Section III imply that state and parameter trajectories can be reconstructed when the relative state trajectories lie within the observable subspace complementary to the subspace outlined in *Proposition 3.1*. This section reconstructs the states and parameters using techniques from system identification. Consider the reduced representation (8) of $n = 3$ agents with unknown parameters k_2 and k_3 . Since the stable equilibrium $\tilde{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{0}$ is unobservable, let the first agent introduce the additive persistent excitation $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ to its nominal control (2) such that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}} &= \begin{bmatrix} -k_1 & k_2 \\ -k_3 & -(k_2 + k_3) \end{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{r}} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{y}} &= [1 \ 0] \tilde{\mathbf{r}} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Fig. 2. Illustration of observer performance for $n = 3$ agent CB Beacon referenced pursuit. (Left) Agent trajectories and the estimated beacon position (dashed black line). (Right) Actual and estimated relative positions.

The system (34) has two unknown parameters k_2 and k_3 . The goal is for agent 1 to estimate the state trajectories \tilde{r} and the unknown parameters k_2, k_3 given only its relative distance measurements between itself and agent two.

The unknown parameter, cyclic pursuit kinematics (34) are in the form of a grey box system identification problem, which is solved using the iterative Gauss-Newton Method [15]. The persistent excitation \tilde{u} is a binary signal with maximum amplitude of two that is composed of five signals with random frequencies between one and ten rad/s. The solver iteratively minimizes the cost function $J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} (\tilde{y}(t) - \hat{\tilde{y}}(t))^2 dt$, where $\tilde{y}(t)$ is the measured output and $\hat{\tilde{y}}(t)$ is generated from the estimated states and parameters.

Table I illustrates the cost function evolution associated with identification of the states and parameters for $n = 3$ agents with unknown initial conditions, unknown parameters $k_2 = 2$ and $k_3 = 0.7$, and known parameter $k_1 = 0.75$. The unknown gains are chosen to avoid the unobservable state configurations derived in Section III. The identification converges to the solution after approximately six iterations and estimates the states and parameters generating the measurement \tilde{y} within numerical tolerances.

Iteration	0	3	6	9	12
Cost Function	0.239	0.023	0.004	6.00e-12	8.98e-32

TABLE I

EVOLUTION OF COST FUNCTION DURING SYSTEM IDENTIFICATION

V. CONCLUSION

This paper considers a variety of cyclic pursuit systems and derives conditions under which states and control parameters can be estimated based on limited sensing by a single “observer” agent. Directions for future work include an analytical proof of the conjectured form of the determinant for observability matrix for beacon-referenced systems (28), as well as more general results for parameter estimation through nonlinear observability approaches and system identification techniques. To address the limitations of our state observation approach for large numbers of agents, current work considers

the employment of teams of observer agents interspersed throughout the collective to improve results.

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